

Potential and Challenges of Regional Integration in the Political Economy of Africa

Christopher Ogola¹

¹ Department of Public Policy and Administration, School of Law, Arts and Social Sciences, Kenyatta University

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ARTICLE INFORMATION	ABSTRACT
<p>Article history: Published on 22 February 2025</p> <p>Keywords: Africa regional development Economic integration in Africa Economic blocs in Africa</p>	<p>This study explored the regional integration in Africa's political economy. The study found that regional integration in Africa has the potential to improve economic markets, provision of public goods and infrastructure, social expenditure, poverty reduction and employment, taxation and revenue generation, money regulation and inflation, peace, security and political stability. Moreover, the study found that several underlying challenges related to inadequate political commitment, poor policy design, inadequate coordination, lack harmonization, weak infrastructural, human and institutional capacity, small economies, limited financial resources, civil wars, interstate conflicts and multiplicity of regional integration schemes are negatively affecting the potential of regional integration in Africa. The study recommends that focus should be made on harmonization of domestic policies with the regional policies to ensure adequate inter-state coordination and regional integration. States should also work towards ensuring adequate institutional, human, infrastructural capacity, factors which are prerequisites of success of a regional integration. Moreover, the political will by the leadership of the member countries should support and ensure that obligations are met as intended.</p>

1. Introduction

In many parts of the world, regional integration is crucial for economic development and, more importantly, for structural transformation toward higher value-added activities such as manufacturing and services. Regional integration is essential for firms and countries to create scale economies and achieve productivity gains through agglomeration. According to McCarthy (2010), regional integration is seen as a rational response to the socio-economic and political difficulties faced by a continent and national markets. On the other hand, the World Bank (2018) reported that regional integration helps countries overcome divisions that impede the flow of goods, services, capital, people and ideas. These divisions are a constraint to economic growth, especially in developing countries. Through regional integration, states agree to cooperate and work closely together to achieve peace, stability and wealth. However, the objectives of regional integration could also involve security and environmental interests. Recently, regional integration has taken the form of a political economy initiative where commercial interests are the focus for achieving broader socio-political, economic and security objectives, as defined by the member states (Erasmus, 2011). Based on political economy, regional integration has led to major developments in international relations between and among many countries, specifically through increases in international trade and investment and in the formation of regional trading blocs. As such, regional integration agreements have gained high importance. Almost all the industrial nations are part of such agreements and a huge number of developing nations are a part of at least one. Advocates of regional integration have further argued that solutions to the global crises must involve regional integration since they transcend national borders and territories, and require the cooperation of different peoples across geography. According to Hartzenberg (2011), the contemporary regional integration agenda not only include investment and competition policy but also a range of other behind-the-border issues that enhance greater economic interdependence between countries.

2. Emergence of regional integration in Africa

2.1 Emergence of regional integration in Africa

Since independence in the 1950s and 1960s, African governments have embraced regional integration as an important component of their development strategy and a means of ensuring competitiveness through the best options available in the field of international trade (Melo & Tsikata, 2014). The failed attempts to industrialize efficiently using import-substitution gave rise to regional integration to facilitate structural

transformation. As a result, African countries adopted regional integration as an economic rational of overcoming the constraint of small and fractioned economies working in isolation (Geda & Seid, 2015). This commitment to regionalism was part of the broader aspiration of Africa to engage at the centre of the global economy and to provide services that could not be provided sufficiently in the absence of some form of intervention of regional integration (Vanheukelom, Byiers & Woolfrey, 2016).

2.2 First generation of regional integration in Africa

The first generation of regional integration schemes were motivated by the political vision of Africa Unity as a means of providing sufficient scale to import substitution policies in the 1960s. However, the regional strategies failed because the national markets at the time were too small and high input costs adversely affected transformation and export, causing foreign exchange shortages and under-valued currencies (Vanheukelom, Byiers & Woolfrey, 2016). According to Dinka & Kennes (2007), domestic monopolies and trade protection contributed to "nationalistic" lobbies that were against regional integration as well as global trade. Moreover, there was excessive emphasis on joint public investments as opposed to creating truly unified markets for the public and private operators (Geda & Seid, 2015). On the other hand, governments with spoken interest in regional cooperation gave token support to regional organizations and in many cases broke their regional commitments that led to implementation lapses (Mistry, 2000).

2.3 Second generation regional integration in Africa

Due to the failure of the first generation regional integration schemes, there was a need for African countries to move from the import-substitution to open-door policies (Olapade, Selormey & Gninafon, 2016). This led to the development of the second-generation regional integration unions in the 1970s. The integration unions were characterized by open regional arrangements for unified markets. There was also renewed political commitment to regional integration from governments and private operators throughout Africa during the period of second-generation integration (Prasad & Songwe, 2021). The second-generation integration schemes have remained important social, economic and political tools for African countries.

3. Africa's regional integration is no longer a matter of choice

Scholarly and policy evidence show that most of Africa's countries still have low per capita income levels and small markets, as is evident from the continent's little share of global production and trade. Scholars and policy makers have therefore pointed out that Africa's regional integrations is no longer a matter of choice (Byiers & Miyandazi, 2021). Against an international backdrop of changing political and economic priorities, Africa has continued to plot new courses for its industrialization and economic development, using the momentum of regional integration (Azirala, Bellon & MacDonald, 2018). With a total of 55 countries and a population of over 1.2 billion people, regional integration has a considerable potential, not only for promoting robust and equitable economic growth, but also for reducing conflict and enhancing trade liberalization among the countries in the continent. According to the United Nations' Economic Commission for Africa (ECA, 2010, p. 23), regional integration is even more important because of the colonial heritage, poverty, insufficient management of public resources and numerous conflicts that exist in the African countries. There is wide recognition that Africa's regional cooperation and integration is vital to tackle challenges in areas ranging from human security, trade, infrastructure, food security, environment and climate change.

4. Selected regional integration organizations in Africa

3.1 West Africa region

In West Africa, the most comprehensive regional initiative is the Economic Community of West African States (ECOWAS). The union was established on 28 May 1975, with the signing of the Treaty of Lagos, with its stated mission to promote economic and political integration across the region. A revised version of the treaty was agreed and signed on 24 July 1993 in Cotonou. Membership of ECOWAS consists of fifteen countries and collectively, the countries comprise an area of 5,114,162 km², an estimated population of over 349 million and a nominal GDP of US\$675 billion. As of January 2022, ECOWAS has six departments consisting of Human Resources Management; Education, Science and Culture; Energy and Mines; Telecommunications and IT; Industry and Private Sector Promotion. The union also serves as a peacekeeping force in the region, with member states occasionally sending joint military forces to intervene in the bloc's member countries at times of political instability and unrest.

3.2 Central and Northern Africa Region

In Central African region, the Economic Community of Central African States (ECCAS) is the principal organization for promotion and of regional economic co-operation among the central African countries. ECCAS was set up in 1983 by eleven Central African States. Its initial goal was to promote exchange and collaboration among the members and give an institutional and legal framework to their cooperation. Recently, ECCAS also aims to achieve collective autonomy, raise the standard of living of its populations and maintain economic stability through harmonious cooperation. Covering an area of 6630539 km², ECCAS has a total population of approximately 158 million with a GDP of \$257.8 billion. The Northern African region has the Arab Maghreb Union (AMU). The union is a trade agreement aiming for economic and political unity among Arab countries in North Africa. Arab Maghreb Union has a nominal GDP US\$382.7 billion, a population of 102 million and an area of 6,046,441 km².

3.3 Southern Africa Region

In Southern Africa region, the main inter-governmental organization is the Southern African Development Community (SADC), headquartered in Gaborone, Botswana. The SADC was formally established in 1980 following the adoption of Lusaka declaration on April, 1980. Its goal was to further regional socio-economic cooperation and integration as well as political and security cooperation among 16 countries in southern Africa. The SADC's activities are coordinated at annual conferences of the heads of government and of a council of ministers from all the member states. The union plans, coordinates, and finances various projects in energy, tourism,

environment, water, mining, employment and labour, culture, information, sports, transport and communications. The SADC Free Trade Area which was established in August 2008, eased access to markets within the zone by the member countries. The SADC member countries cover a total area of 9,672,702 km², a population of 363 million and a nominal GDP of US\$597.8 billion.

3.4 Eastern Africa Region

In East Africa, the East African Community (EAC) is the major intergovernmental organization composed of six countries in the African Great Lakes region in East Africa. The countries include Burundi, Kenya, Rwanda, South Sudan, Tanzania, and Uganda. The organization was founded in 1967, collapsed in 1977, and was revived in 2000. The East Africa Community was established with a vision to set up a prosperous, competitive, secure, stable and politically united East Africa; and provide platform to widen and deepen economic, political, social and culture integration in order to improve the quality of life of the people in the member countries. In 2010, the EAC launched its own common market for goods, labour and capital within the region, with the goal of creating a common currency to increase competitiveness, value added production, trade and investments. The East African Community had a total population of 184 million, a landmass area of 2,467,202 km² and a nominal GDP of US\$ 220.783 billion.

5. Potential of regional integration in the political economy of Africa

5.1 Regional integration and Economic Markets in Africa

The intra-regional trade has remained consistently low compared with its intercontinental trade (Economic Commission for Africa, 2010). More than 80 percent of Africa's exports are still destined for outside markets, with the European Union (EU) and the United States accounting for more than 50 percent of this total. Asia, and China in particular, are also important export markets for African countries and regional economic blocks. At the same time, the combined African imports is more than 90 percent of her goods from outside the continent (Economic Commission for Africa, 2011). However, regional integration has been important in addressing the problem of tiny markets within the African countries that have created many trade-offs between economies of scale and competition. By enlarging markets, regional integration has the potential to remove a number of these trade-offs and make possible the existence of larger firms with greater productive efficiency for any industry with economies of scale (African Development Bank, 2018). Trade liberalization through reduction of tariffs and other trade barriers is one of the major strategies that regional markets have used to allow member countries access larger markets. According to World Trade Organization (2011), market access within African countries has the potential to increase competition that induces firms to cut prices, expand sales and reduce internal inefficiencies. Consequently, competition may lead to the rationalization of production and the removal of inefficient duplication of plants. For instance, within the East African Community (EAC), access to larger markets has enabled the member countries to double their exports and imports. An annual report by Tanzania's Central Bank indicated that Tanzania exported goods worth US\$811.2 million to the EAC member countries in 2020 up from US\$678.5 million in the previous year. In the same period, the regional block enabled Kenya to increase exports from US\$1.28 billion in 2019 to US\$1.44 billion in 2020 (KNBS, Economic Survey 2021).

Intra-regional exports have been growing in value across other regional blocks. Over the 2000 to 2009 period, intra-regional exports accounted for 9.7 percent of total exports in SADC, 5.3 percent in COMESA, 19.8 percent in the EAC, 8.8 percent in ECOWAS, and 0.8 percent in ECCAS. In 2009, intra-regional exports accounted for 10.8 percent of total exports in SADC, 7.1 percent in COMESA, 18.9 percent in the EAC, 9.9 percent in ECOWAS and 0.6 in ECCAS.

Table 1. Intra-regional exports, 2000 - 2009 (US\$ millions)

RECs	2000	2001	2002	2003	2004	2005	2006	2007	2008	2009	Average 2000-09
COMESA	1442.8	1626.3	1739.1	2004.2	2293.2	2694.6	2917.7	4021.2	6676.1	6114.2	3152.9
EAC	689.4	753.3	804.4	878.5	1006.3	1075.3	1061.5	1385.2	1797	1572.2	1102.3

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ECCAS	181.6	193.4	186.4	183.2	218.9	254.6	312.8	385.4	449.2	378.3	274.4
ECOWAS	2714.9	2241.9	3135.9	3037.2	4366.1	5497.5	5901.6	6716.7	9355.2	7312.0	5027.9
SADC	4460.7	4047.7	4597.1	5649.5	6636.2	7769.6	8598.2	11873.7	15895.6	11599.4	8112.8

Source: IMF DOTS (2011)

Intra-regional imports have also shown a growing trend. Between 2000 and 2009, intra-regional imports averaged 9.5 percent in SADC, 5.4 percent in COMESA, 8 percent in the EAC, 9.6 percent in ECOWAS, and 1.8 percent in ECCAS. In 2009, intra-regional imports accounted for 10 percent of SADC's

total imports, 5.8 percent for COMESA, 7.6 percent for the EAC, 8.1 percent for ECOWAS, and 1.2 percent for ECCAS. (12 percent); and in ECCAS, 52 percent of imports were destined for two countries – Gabon (29 percent) and Chad (24%)

Table 2. Intra-regional imports, 2000 - 2009 (US\$ millions)

RECs	2000	2001	2002	2003	2004	2005	2006	2007	2008	2009	Average 2000-09
COMESA	1394.6	1674.4	1871.4	2203.2	2424.3	3998.1	4461.8	4644.5	7756.9	6890.7	3732.0
EAC	512.3	489.9	551.8	786.9	895.7	1170.4	1160.7	1515.2	1969.4	1723	1077.5
ECCAS	207.3	218.5	186.3	213.5	242.1	281.6	346.0	426.2	496.8	418.4	303.7
ECOWAS	2473.6	2695.6	2477.9	3293.1	4718.7	5835.0	6391.8	7281.0	10142.0	7950.3	5325.9
SADC	4026.3	4061.5	4415.0	4831.4	6973.9	7743.1	9654.9	12447.2	16687.0	12089.9	8293.0

Source: IMF DOTS (2011)

Between 2000 and 2007, intra-regional exports in Africa registered a growth rate of 15 percent, while intra-regional imports recorded a growth rate of 18% (Economic Commission for Africa, 2011).

5.2 Regional integration, provision of Public Goods and Infrastructure in Africa

In many countries in Africa, national public goods have small market sizes due to fragmentation. The supply of these goods therefore becomes more cost effective in larger sub-regional markets. Regional integration has enabled African countries to export and access public goods that markets are lacking or cannot be produced. The goods generate shared benefits for the participating countries. One example is the Desert to Power Initiative, promoted by the Community of Sahel–Saharan States (CENSAD) aimed at connecting 250 million people with green electricity through a combination of public, private, on-grid and off-grid projects by 2025. In Southern Africa region, the Southern African Power Pool, is being advocated by the SADC member countries to act as a regional market mechanism for channeling a small part of regional electricity trade. In 2015, 6 percent of regional electricity trade in the Southern African Power Pool was channeled through the pool's market mechanism.

According to the African Centre for Transport, Infrastructure and Regional Integration (ACTIRI, 2022), there is a compelling case for regional integration in Africa as the right strategy for developing its required transport infrastructure. Infrastructure is one of the most critical enablers of a successful regional integration, taking into account its importance in facilitating activities such as trade, agriculture, tourism and the movement of labour and other resources. Regional organizations are therefore coordinating, harmonizing and complementing transport and communications policies in order to improve and expand the existing transport and communication links as a means of furthering the physical cohesion of the Partner States.

The regional transport infrastructure and support services cover roads, railways, civil aviation, maritime transport and ports, multi-modal transport, freight administration and management. A number of Tripartite Agreements have also been reached in the field of infrastructure including telecommunications and Inland Waterway Transport systems provide a facilitative instrument to regulate inland waterways transport (African Development Bank, 2020).

In East Africa Community, member countries are promoting telecommunication links through the East Africa One Network Area (ONA).

The ONA is part of the East Africa Single Digital Market Initiative, focused on a single connectivity market, a single data market and seamless digital content access. In 2015, the ONA was set up to harmonize mobile phone markets across the East African Community. The aimed was to reduce and ultimately eliminate roaming charges for calls across the member country borders. ONA also stipulated waivers of excise taxes and surcharges on incoming ONA voice traffic and wholesale and retail price caps on outbound traffic. In mid-2015, ONA was extended to data and mobile money transactions, both key to developing cross-border trade and regional value chains. After ONA implementation, inbound roaming calls to Kenya from Rwanda increased by more than tenfold and retail roaming rates in Uganda dropped eightfold (World Bank, 2016). Cross-border traffic tripled in both Kenya and Uganda and increased nearly fivefold in Rwanda and thirtyfold in South Sudan.

A report by African Development Bank (2017) indicated that Africa needs a deliberate, systematic and concerted effort at the practical level to integrate, upgrade and modernize regional infrastructure so that it becomes the catalyze economic growth. Regionally integrated corridor approaches will offer prospects for speedier integration of infrastructure systems in Africa. The ultimate objective for Africa should be to create a single market of 750 million people that is competitive within itself and within the global economy. The way forward is to put in place a goal oriented, results driven, continent-wide framework for addressing Africa's regional infrastructure needs on an integrated basis (Africa Development Bank, 2010). This should have a practical approach to evolving an integrated, coordinated and efficient African regional infrastructure system that is supportive and facilitative of the ultimate goal of creating a vibrant single African market. In this light, creation of a Framework for African Regional Infrastructure Cooperation (ADB, 2010) will further harmonize frameworks for supporting regional infrastructure development, integration and operation across the African countries.

5.3 Regional integration, Social Expenditure, Poverty Reduction and Employment in Africa

An empirical investigation by Madeira (2014) on the relationship between regional integration and social spending revealed that regionalization has a significant and positive relationship with government social spending and poverty reduction. According to Madeira, regional economic and political integration does not necessarily lead to a "race to the bottom" of social spending. Instead, regionalization appears to accommodate a wider divergence in national social policy commitments that in turn enhance social spending and development. The study, which was conducted in the Caribbean countries, contradicted the common perception that regional spending leads to reduction in social spending and development in the developing countries. Regional integration could have positive social

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outcomes if developing countries (such as those in Africa) compensate society for economic insecurity with increased social spending or if the social policies are created at the supranational level. Other scholars have

found that the insecurities imposed on social groups by global competition fuel demands for states to increase social spending (Madeira, 2014).

Figure 1. Increasing social spending as a percentage of total government expenditures.

Source: Madeira, 2014.

Similarly, in Africa, increased intra-trade between countries has boosted economic performance, which in turn, led to a slight increase in social spending and poverty reduction. The case of East Africa Community member countries is a prime example. World Bank data (2017) indicate that the member countries have generally improved in social and poverty indicators between 1990 and 2014. The reduction in absolute poverty is a

natural outcome of the sustained growth in real per capita GDP in those countries in the same period. Moreover, improvement in educational outcomes was another major driver of progress in the East Africa Community countries (UNCTAD, 2016). East African Community also showed remarkable annual 2.6% growth in human development from 2000 to 2010 in comparison to Africa's 1.7%.

Table 3: Poverty and inequality indicators in EAC member states (1991-2013)

	Burundi			Kenya		Rwanda		United Republic of Tanzania			Uganda		
	1992	2006	2014	1992	2005	2005	2013	1991	2007	2011	1992	2005	2012
Gini index	33.3	33.4	...	57.5	48.5	52.0	50.4	35.3	40.3	37.8	41.4	42.9	41.0
Poverty ratio (World Bank)	81.1	77.7	...	23.1	33.6	68.0	60.4	70.4	52.7	46.6	68.1	53.2	34.6
Poverty ratio	...	67.1	64.6	57.2 ^a	45.9	56.7	39.1 ^b	38.6 ^a	34.4 ^a	28.2	56.4	31.1	19.5
Rural poverty ratio	68.8	46.5 ^a	49.1	61.9	43.7 ^b	40.8 ^a	39.1 ^a	33.3	60.3	34.2	22.4
Urban poverty ratio	27.6	29.3 ^a	33.7	28.5	15.9 ^b	28.5 ^a	20.0 ^a	15.5	28.8	13.7	9.6

Source: World Bank, 2017.

In the West African region, the ECOWAS member countries have made significant strides in the healthcare sector, by increasing health expenditure as a percentage of GDP. Through the West African Health Organization (WAHO), ECOWAS countries have created an environment that is more supportive of healthcare research at institutional, national and regional levels. The countries also adopted the ECOWAS Regional Pharmaceutical Plan (ERPP), to provide a framework to strengthen the pharmaceutical manufacturing industry in West Africa and to create a conducive environment for making quality, safe and affordable drugs in the region.

In terms of employment, African Development Bank (2017) indicated that regional integration in Africa has the potential to generate greater benefits including job creation given the high unemployment levels. Moreover, the African Economic Research Consortium (AERC, 2019) reported that labour mobility and wage flexibility could address regional employment, labour market and wage imbalances. In addition, the common markets may lead to convergence of level of wage employment in the integrated regional labour market.

5.4 Regional integration, Taxation and Revenue generation in Africa

The ultimate goal of regional integration is the long-term high economic growth for member states (Ogunniyi, et al., 2014). Tax revenues contribute to the stability of government income allows countries to provide public goods and services. For this reason, regional organizations in Africa consider the critical role of tax revenues for countries to create room in their budgets, in order to increase spending on social services like health, education, public investment and filling infrastructure gaps. Moreover, with the increasing debts of many African countries, raising tax revenues is the most growth-friendly way to stabilize debt. Tax revenues are critical to achieving stability given the high dependence of developing countries on

this fiscal revenue. Creating larger markets for goods and services produced in the region, regional integration has the potential to boost revenue among the member states in Africa. Several empirical investigations have shown that regional integration contributes to more revenue for the member countries. For instance, using data from 1980-2004, Ogunniyi et al. (2014) found that regional integration in Africa has had a significant positive impact on tax revenue within the regional organizations. A report by SADC revealed the same trend by showing a higher average intra-trade revenue collection of the member countries, between 2007 and 2018 (SADC, 2021).

Table 3: SADC intra-trade average revenue collection by member countries

Year	2007	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018
% GDP	27.2	28.9	25.6	26.6	27.8	27.6	26.8	25.9	24.5	23.1	23.0	24.1

Source: SADC, 2021.

5.5 Regional integration, Money Regulation and Inflation thresholds in Africa

The effect of monetary regulation an inflation on economic growth is not a new issue in many countries, due to their role on micro and macro-economic stability. Regional integration organizations Africa have therefore adopted specific policy instruments to eliminate trade barriers and coordinate monetary and fiscal policies. The policies are important in addressing inflation threshold that is necessary to support economic growth and enabling the countries to transition to more integrated regional monetary economies. According to Houeninvo & Boko (2007), the level of inflation needed to sustain growth is between 1 and 5% for developed countries and between 9 and 20% for developing and low-income countries. Similarly, there is need for a maximum inflation threshold that countries should not cross for economic growth. Consequently, there is an inflation interval, within which inflation has a positive effect on economic growth (Houeninvo & Boko, 2007).

In the West African region, ECOWAS countries are in the process of forming an efficient and viable monetary union. At the thirty-fifth ECOWAS

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Conference of Heads of State, the member countries proposed an inflation threshold of 5%. According to the Conference of Heads of State, the proposed threshold was meant to contribute towards economic stability – which encourages saving, investment, economic growth, and help in maintaining international competitiveness. The Conference emphasized on the existence of an optimal inflation interval within which the inflation of the west African countries can support economic growth. The member nations are working to harmonize their national, social, taxation, monetary and fiscal policies and let them be administered by the regional organization. Such economic arrangements are common in developed nations. For example in Europe, regional integration like the European Union involves monetary union dimension where members agree to unify their national monetary policies to be administered by the supranational monetary authority (Houeninvo & Boko, 2007).

In the SADC regional block, member countries are developing the Monetary Union in order to achieve macroeconomic convergence, harmonize exchange rates systems, liberalize capital and current accounts transactions and adopt market-oriented approaches to the conduct of monetary policy. Establishing the Monetary Union in the SADC region is not only the ultimate goal of the SADC Protocol on Trade, but also a key milestone in the drive for deeper integration in SADC. Such establishments enhance regional monetary cooperation by reforming payment systems and harmonizing legal operational frameworks for central banks in implementation of the best banking practices (SADC, 2022). Other policies adopted by the Monetary Union include a common external tariff policy, liberalization of the intra-union trade through the elimination of non-tariff barriers and progressive reduction of tariff rates within the community. In addition, the Union aims to harmonize and coordinate institutional frameworks, public finance, statistical record-keeping, fiscal legislation and accounting practices, which have hitherto been different according to each country in the SADC block (SADC, 2021).

However, starting a monetary union with over or undervalued exchange rates could create rapid inflation in African countries (Durevali, 2011). According to Adams (2005), monetary unification is a good opportunity to promote the harmonization of financial, banking and political systems that in turn increases the efficiency and development of African countries individually. Gupta (2010) noted that coordinating the exchange rates of the various countries, with the objective of moving towards a single currency helps to achieve economic objectives. African regional integration blocks are in the process of deepening economic integration with implementation of regional single currency. In the SADC block, tested on the current Common Monetary Area countries that use the South African Rand (South Africa, Lesotho, Namibia and Swaziland) and if successful, will be ready to be rolled out to the rest of the SADC Member States as the region advances its integration process. In East African Community, the Monetary Union Protocol aims to harmonize policies and requisite institutions to attain a single currency.

5.6 Regional integration, Peace, Security and political stability in Africa

In the face of Africa's multiple security threats, integration and regionalization are increasingly seen as providing opportunities for establishing sustainable economic growth, peace and stability, and

securing democratic consolidation (Wachira, 2004). Thus, regional integration and co-operation groupings are emerging as conflict managers in their respective regions. In response to regional conflict, some regional organizations have come up with early warning and response apparatus, such as the ECOWAS Early Warning Mechanism. Through the mechanism, ECOWAS played a major role in preventing further atrocities in the Côte d'Ivoire conflicts of 2002 (Kode, 2016). The intervention of ECOWAS in the conflict indicated the important role of regional integration in addressing peace and security challenges in Africa.

A similar program by Inter-Governmental Authority on Development, Conflict Early Warning and Response Mechanism (IGAD CEWARN). The mechanism aims to deepen the commitment by Member States on early warning information sharing as well as joint response actions in response to emerging threats of violent conflict. In the East Africa, the East Africa Community has developed a Strategy for Regional Peace and Security (SRPS) that spells out the areas of cooperation for the Community in a bid to ensure peace and security in the broader East Africa region (EAC, 2013). The SRPS aims to drive the EAC regional security agenda and bond it together as a political federation capable of resolving its conflict and safety related issues, as enshrined in the EAC Treaty (Anjalo, Okoth & Kimokoti, 2018). In the southern Africa, the SADC has supported mediation and preventive diplomacy efforts across many countries through the Regional Indicative Strategic Development Plan (RISDP). Under the Peace, Security, and Good Governance foundational pillar, RISDP aims to enhance conflict prevention, management, and resolution mechanisms with an effective early warning system capable of tracking and monitoring political, security, and socio-economic threats.

In general, the regional integration organizations have a greater role in maintaining peace, security and stability of the African countries. Moreover, regional consider peace and security as the necessary preconditions for regional development because instability in one Member State has a negative impact on neighboring countries and become an obstacle in regional integration. Projects such as the New Partnership for Africa's Development (NEPAD), the UN Millennium Declaration, and the newly launched African Union (AU) have further emphasized the role of regional economic communities in responding to Africa's challenges (Kode, 2016). The intended outcomes of peace and security by regional integration include strengthening early warning systems; enhancing conflict mediation, promoting preventative diplomacy, resolving disputes and developing strategies to address transnational organized crime.

Recently, interstate and civil conflicts have reduced in Africa, thanks to the added efforts of regional integration peace making programs. A report by PRIO Armed Conflict Database showed that interstate conflict remains a rare event in Africa. Since 1990, there have been seven wars between states in total, the latest of which took place in 2016 between Ethiopia and Eritrea. Moreover, intrastate conflict in Africa are related to the rise and expansion of the Islamic State in Niger, Chad, Nigeria, Libya, Burkina Faso, Mali, Somalia, and Mozambique. However, the regional organizations are developing new mechanisms on a "Common Position Against Terrorism", to deal with the new threat of radicalization across the African countries.

Figure 2: African Conflicts (1946-2020);

Source: UCDP Database, 2020.

6. Identified challenges undermining regional integration in the political economy of Africa

6.1 Inadequate political will and commitment

It takes political will and commitment to build and nurture Africa's regional integration arrangements toward the long-held aspiration and vision of continental union (Dinka & Kennes, 2007). At the country level, such commitment would be demonstrated by going beyond regular

participation in meetings of integration institutions, to active encouragement and involvement in all aspects of their operations. However, many governments in Africa consistently fail to meet their financial and implementation-related undertakings for regional integration. Tafirenyika (2014) gave the example of the Southern African Development Community (SADC). The SADC Trade Protocol has a provision that allows exemptions from phasing out tariffs. Some countries have applied for such

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exemptions, but others have simply reintroduced the tariffs or alternative instruments such as domestic taxes. This demonstrates a lack of political will to implement agreed obligations. Some member states recognize belatedly the implications of the agreements they have signed and no longer want to be bound by them.

6.2 Poor design, inadequate coordination and lack harmonization of integration policies

Policy makers need to show consistency and coherence on the objectives and policies being pursued with regard to regional integration. Policies on regional integration should be unified by establishing appropriate coordination mechanisms and by creating a clear focal point. National consensus together with clarity on policies and structural issues helps to advance the integration agenda at the country level (Sako, 2006). In many African countries, however, poorly designed policies, inadequate inter-state coordination and lack of harmonization presents a great challenge to regional integration. Ambiguous policies characterized by fragmentation, unclear prioritization and poor sequencing of programs and activities are common in the regional blocks in Africa (Geda & Seid, 2015; Qobo, 2007; Strachan, 2018).

6.3 Weak infrastructural, human and institutional capacity

Weak infrastructural capacity exacerbates the geographical constraints of African countries and keeps their economies apart (African Development Bank, 2010). Most African countries are still dependent on the infrastructure inherited from the colonial time, which was not developed to foster intra-African economic relations. There has been under-investment in new infrastructure, with important country variations. According to the United Nations Development Program (UNDP, 2014), the absence or weakness of physical infrastructure limits the potential human development impacts of regional integration in Africa. Moreover, institutional capacities and policies further undermine the infrastructural linkages in the continent. In addition, other non-policy factors operating in the sub-region's economies such as weak financial and administrative capabilities also explain the discrepancies between policies and outcomes, and the shared failures of the regional integration organizations.

6.4 Small economies, limited financial resources and inadequate funding

If individual countries are small in economic size, it is reasonable that a combination of several such countries in the context of regional integration scheme, would bring about a sufficiently large market size to generate lower production cost and compete with the rest of the world (Oyejide, 2000). According to Melo & Tsikata (2015), the small, sparsely populated, fragmented and often isolated economies across Africa make a compelling case for these economies to integrate regionally to reap efficiency gains, exploit economies of scale and reduce the thickness of borders. However, lack of complementarities among partners and diminishing returns to the exploitation of resources has reduced supply response to market-integration oriented regional policies. The small markets with low income affect generation of adequate revenues needed to fund and implement various regional integration projects. The regional integration member

countries have to depend on external funding by foreign countries, which expose them to vulnerability due to the expensive debts. In the sub-Saharan region, for instance, foreign external debts increased from US\$200 billion to US\$ 360 billion between 2006 and 2013 (United Nations Conference on Trade and Development, UNCTAD, 2017).

Figure: Debt of Sub-Saharan Africa (2000-2013);

Source: UNCTAD, 2017.

6.5 Civil wars, interstate conflicts and political instability

Africa is one of the most economically integrated continents in terms of the number of regional trade agreements within the region, but trade between African countries remains only around 10% of Africa's total trade, much lower than levels observed in other continents. The first important challenge in the economic integration process in Africa is political stability. Many policy analyses have found political instability as one of the major issues behind the struggling regional trade agreements in Africa. Domestic political instability is the main source of uncertainty for the trade agreements in Africa, as recently highlighted in international trade literature. Even after trade agreements come into force, the possibility of termination of the agreements becomes very high. An example is the political conflict in Sierra Leone and Liberia that made the Mano River Union (MRU), one of regional trade agreements in the ECOWAS region, impotent (Jung, 2017). Political instability discourages efficient negotiations between African countries and makes it difficult to implement trade agreements (Molders, 2016).

6.6 Multiplicity of regional integration schemes

Africa has the highest density of economic integration and cooperation arrangements. Yet, these arrangements have failed to impact positively on the Continent's economic performance. Overlapping membership of countries across regional integration cooperation has been found to add constraints to the capacity and resources of the member countries. According to UNECA (2006) survey of regional integration in Africa, overlapping memberships make it difficult for African countries to pay their dues to various regional integrations. Moreover, the multiple regional schemes create conflicting and duplicative program implementation and limit meeting attendance by the member countries (UNECA 2006). Since the socio-economic and political models underpinning the formations are different, the multi-level strategies that governments have to pursue negate the benefits of regional integration (Deacon, Ortiz & Zelenev, 2007).

Figure: Regional arrangements in Africa;

Source: Acharya et al., (2011); WTO, (2015)

7. Discussion and conclusion

African economic integration remains a critical pillar for the continent's industrialization and political economy (Houeninvo & Boko, 2007). The integrations agreements have the potential to enable the member countries to build stronger and more resilient economies. Even though Africa has the world's lowest share of regional trade and investment, the potential for growth of intra-trade is high (Durevall, 2011; Jung, 2017). A scan through the literature, empirical investigations and policy documents reveal that recently, the regional integrations have increased the size of economic markets and improved provision of public goods and infrastructure. The regional integrations have encouraged social expenditure, poverty reduction and created more employment. By boosting taxation, regional integration has enabled countries to generate more revenue. Furthermore, the regional integrations have facilitated money regulation and inflation control and enhanced peace, security and political stability in Africa.

However, it is necessary that a number of constraints and obstacles at the national and regional level be removed if the full potential of integration is to be realized. The first and most important focus should be on harmonization of domestic policies with the regional policies to ensure adequate inter-state coordination and regional integration. The policies must be clear to allow effective sequencing of programs with the other countries within the regional block. States should also work towards ensuring adequate institutional, human and infrastructural capacity, factors which are prerequisites of success of a regional integration. Moreover, the political will by the leadership of the member countries should support and ensure that obligations are met as intended. This may involve provision of the required resources, improving the state capacity, enacting regional-friendly laws and contributing actively to the implementation of common goals within the regional block. For member countries to realize their goal of integration agreement, they must ensure that there is peace and security within their borders and limit their membership to a reasonable number of integration organizations.

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